

A PATH ON THE UNDERSTANDING DIFFICULTIES OF TRIGONOMETRIC CONCEPTS IN THE 1ST YEAR OF HIGH SCHOOL

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7046482

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Summary

This article sought to analyze the trajectory of the legal apparatus of mathematics teaching in Brazil, with a main focus on the difficulties of understanding trigonometric concepts in high school, and, more specifically, with first-year students. The general objective of the article is to present how these difficulties were built over time and how to solve them through active teaching methodologies. To achieve this objective, a research was carried out on the National Curricular Parameters (PCN), on the National Curricular Common Base and on other literature to prove that teaching through these methodologies can result in a better use of school learning. There is also a reflection on what should be the role of the teacher in the classroom as a mediator of knowledge. Finally, some methodologies and strategies that can help in teaching-learning are considered in a way that allows the expression and creativity of the student as an active subject in the creation of knowledge.

Keywords: trigonometric concepts; teaching mathematics; high school; active methodologies.

INTRODUCTION

This article proposes a reflective and at the same time critical look at the difficulties of learning in Mathematics, more specifically, of understanding trigonometric concepts among students of the first year of High School, in addition to, after this survey of difficulties, trying to establish the role of the teacher during the process and possible pedagogical practices. If

possible, point out some differences between learning difficulties and learning disorders, and how to act in both cases.

Commonly, there is evidence of several students with specific traumas in the Mathematics discipline and, therefore, it is necessary to adopt ways to minimize such negative impacts so that it does not become a burden to the student, even though he/she receives the discipline with greater difficulty, one of the roles central to the school, is to ensure that there is inclusion and perception, so that it can be remedied in time to do the best possible, whether the student has learning difficulties or not.

Going through the paths and lines of thought of specific authors who have already traced research on the subject, it is important to go back to a historical and legal context of Mathematics so that, only later, to understand the difficulties and effective practices so that the most accurate development can be achieved. Learning according to Vygotsky is a lasting modification of behavior, which occurs through training, experience and observation. "From the moment the individual modifies this experience, becoming significant and continuous, it can be considered that he has learned" (COELHO; PISONI, 2012, p. 144).

Guiomar Namó de Mello (1986), discusses the role of the school in this learning, namely, "School is expected to produce such a variety of social results that it will hardly be able to produce even under ideal conditions" (MELLO, 1986, p. 17) . There are numerous reasons that can end up hindering the learning of Mathematics, among them, malnutrition, fighting crime, emotional problems, family disorganization, in addition to learning difficulties related to disorders that interfere with the brain's ability to learn.

Learning difficulties in Mathematics have been discussed in different instances, from mathematical literacy to high school – which is the focus of this research. In addition, the perception of learning difficulties with the way in which it is transmitted by teachers also constitutes a relationship, either by the way the teacher designs this teaching, and how the student receives it, in both cases when there are learning disorders and when there is no identification of the same, or if the strategies are not attractive to students, there is school failure. According to the National Curriculum Guidelines, the school's principle is to guarantee access to knowledge and elements of culture that are essential to a common formation, but this does not happen unilaterally, as each one learns individually according to their genetic, physical and psychological availability. (BRAZIL, 1996).

About this Carvalho (2001), mentions that it is useless to make up the results, because we must be against the statistical make-up of ignorance and the failure of the teaching system. In order for knowledge to be effectively democratized and the approval numbers to present real

advances in learning, it is necessary not only to change a supposed “repetition culture” and to implement new evaluation concepts, but also to offer resources to schools, from small classes, adequate spaces and pedagogical materials to an effective work of school recovery and conditions for the constant training of teaching professionals (CARVALHO, 2001, p.250).

Learning difficulties have been a subject widely discussed and researched historically and over time, the advances of these researches have been significant to find various types of disorders related to learning, among them pathologies that make the brain not receive and assimilate the information.

DEVELOPMENT HISTORICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF MATHEMATICS

In 1955, in Bahia, there was the first National Teaching Congress with the aim of discussing teaching improvements in schools, including in the field of Mathematics. Then, in the 1960s, mathematics teaching began to be strongly influenced by a movement known as the International Movement of Modern Mathematics. The mentioned retro movement was one of the arms of Jean Piaget's pedagogical precepts, with the aim of helping the child in the construction of the concept of set, which is the basis of operational thinking. However, in practice, what was seen was the teaching of Set Theory in the first grades of elementary school, totally disconnected from Piaget's constructivist idea, that is, without worrying about the construction of knowledge by the student.

As the teaching of Mathematics in the early years was restricted to the abstract study of Sets and of a more formal Mathematics, the Movement in Brazil was not successful and soon dispersed, due to the absence of satisfactory results. Despite being a very brief movement, this was the kick-off to arouse interest in research into new methodologies for teaching Mathematics. However, the need to develop new methodologies was only observed by professionals in the area some time later, building the concern that students participate in the construction of knowledge, achieving the necessary skills for life in society. Michele Silva (2015) lists these competencies as follows:

“a) Mathematics teaching was based on everyday problems and other areas of knowledge; b) exploration of various contents, occupation in a balanced and articulated way of numbers and operations, space and form, magnitudes and measures, in addition to the treatment of information, including elements of statistics, probability and combinatorics; c) responsible use of available technological resources: video, calculator, computer, among others, as true learning tools” (SILVA *apud* DANTZIG, 2015, p. 4).

The proposals by Danzig (1970) and Silva (2015) expect that students, first in Elementary School and, later, in High School, concatenate their mathematical skills with various fields such as arithmetic, algebra, trigonometry, geometry, probability, statistics and logical reasoning. The articulation must occur not only in the curricular scope, but with a focus on the subject's life, so that education is related to their idea of citizenship.

This training, with the main objective being the social, has its beginning in the initial grades of Elementary School to allow the student, even at a young age, to perceive himself as an active subject in the teaching-learning process within the environment in which he lives and studies. To corroborate this statement, the Law of Directives and Bases approved in 1996 establishes as mandatory the training process that covers the world beyond the walls of the school.

“Art. 2nd. Education, a duty of the family and the State, inspired by the principles of freedom and the ideals of human solidarity, aims at the full development of the student, his preparation for the exercise of citizenship and his qualification for work” (BRASIL, 1996, p. 1). Law no. 9.394/1996, both in Art. 2 and in Art. 22, presents three different fields, citizenship, work and education so that the student leaves the school stage with the cognitive ability to create, participate, act and understand and relate Mathematics consciously to the dynamics of society. In this way, teaching takes place in a meaningful and coherent way with the student's social reality.

In 2000, some adjustments to the National Curriculum Parameters were approved and articulated, namely, the Ministry of Education (MEC) proposed as purposes for the Teaching of Mathematics: “to identify mathematical knowledge as a means to understand and transform the world to the around them, [...] communicate mathematically and [...] feel secure in their own ability to build mathematical knowledge” (BRASIL, 2000, p. 37).

In this wake, Jean Piaget (1976-1977) reminds us that both children and young people are not static beings, they deal with the environment, with people and experience experiences that will make them adapt to the environment. If the learner is dynamic, it makes no sense for education to be static. The educator who proposes to teach Mathematics needs to be able to interact in an articulated way and with experiences directed to the school age in question. About this, Silva *et al.* (2004) comment:

“in our days, the use, with understanding, of the fundamental arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication and division) has become one of the main objectives of any Basic Mathematics Education. It is necessary to keep in mind the importance of developing the understanding of meaning and the use of operations in solving the various problems of everyday life, which is

more important than the simple mastery of algorithms” (SILVA, LOURENÇO and CÔGO, 2004, P. 71).

Thus, it is understood that when working with trigonometric concepts, it is necessary to reach these competences leaving the static and traditional method. The system is still rigid and that is why high school students, specifically in the first year, often have difficulties in assimilating these concepts. Therefore, it would be necessary that these were worked in a clear way, with mastery and updating of the teacher without ignoring the social side of each student, helping in their personal interests and not facing Mathematics only as a mandatory subject.

Thinking within this spectrum, starting in 2017, the National Curricular Common Base was approved, which aims to ensure that, nationwide, all students have the right and access to the same curriculum throughout basic education (kindergarten, elementary and secondary education). high school). For this research, it is interesting to focus on the area of “Mathematics and its Technologies” in which some skills are presented - specific competences 3, 4 and 5 - that need to be acquired during this school process.

The specific competences of the teaching of Mathematics and its Technologies in High School presented in the BNCC (Base Nacional Comum Curricular), according to the document itself, have the objective of expanding and deepening what was learned during the nine years of Elementary School, for Therefore, five defined skills are presented to assist the teacher in the construction of their classes and objectives. Among the five, a brief analysis will be made of the three focused on the area of Trigonometry.

When observing the documents presented so far and comparing them to BNCC, a relevant change in the content teaching proposal can be seen, since, previously, the concern was mainly with the cycle and trigonometric equations, and from the Base, the The focus is on the trigonometric cycle and its more analytical, that is, reflective, contents.

1. LEARNING DIFFICULTIES IN TRIGONOMETRY

Thinking about the teaching of Trigonometry within the school itself is a subject that demands some attention, because this subject is in a difficult to understand track. Scholars Demir & Heck (2013) state that “the complex nature of trigonometry makes it challenging for the student to understand the topic in a deep and conceptual way”. Furthermore, Weber (2005, p.91) also states that “trigonometry is one of the first topics in mathematics that relates algebraic, geometric and graphic reasoning”. Both thoughts make it evident that this first contact with different reasoning makes the period of High School dense in the area in focus.

Meanwhile, MARCHAND (2009, p.64) explains that the development of geometric thinking takes place in five levels, and that, unfortunately, it is not possible to pass to the next level in a satisfactory way if all the expected skills of the level have not been obtained. previous. In this way, it is necessary to improve the levels of reasoning so that there is a chronological order that needs to be followed and that each student reaches such levels in a natural and organized way, depending on the teacher only as a facilitator of the whole process.

That said, it is obvious that there is a need for first year high school students to reach these levels of geometric reasoning in their first contact with trigonometry so that, when they reach this level, they can progress in a fluid and consistent way. In this aspect, Weber (2005, p.91) shows that “many high school and university students are not used to this type of reasoning.”, which necessarily becomes a problem.

When looking at these difficulties and lags that come from the previous cycle, one of the possibilities of these unfinished concepts may be the little importance given to geometry when inserted in the school curriculum. Despite all the legal apparatus already presented, when we look at the textbooks, we can see a closer look at algebra content, including the training of some teachers who were also victims of this lag, creating a repetitive cycle.

This cycle began to be changed in short steps in the 1990s when the National Curricular Parameters (PCNs) presented a new format for teaching Trigonometry, which was recently founded in the 2000s with the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) that encourages research and more active methodologies in the teaching of Mathematics. Two researchers, Fátima Queiroz Dionízio and Célia Fink Brandt, in 2011 carried out a survey with some students of the 1st year of high school in order to find out what their main difficulties were in assimilating content in Trigonometry. After some interviews, questionnaires, activities and conversations with the students and the teacher, they came to the conclusion that:

Analyzing the students' procedures, it was possible to observe the difficulty that students have in understanding and conceptualizing mathematical objects in trigonometry, when using different representations of a mathematical object, as if these representations did not refer to that same object [...] it was possible to perceive how much difficulty students have in correctly converting to figurative language due to semantic non-congruence. This question allows a reflection on ways to minimize the difficulties arising from semantic non-congruence and its cognitive cost that influences the student's success or failure in many mathematical situations (BRANDT; DIONÍZIO, 2011, p. 4420).

Therefore, it can be concluded that the teaching of Trigonometry is a teaching-learning area that needs to be observed and researched more closely by Mathematics teachers, both in

Elementary School and High School, even reaching the research inside the walls of the school. academia so that it reaches those who are or will be responsible for the construction of textbooks, changes in curricula, among other factors that are directly linked to students' understanding of the content.

This importance is not only due to the satisfaction with school performance in the form of evaluations, but also in the ability to relate their experiences with everyday life in their logical, algebraic and geometric reasoning as well as the ability to abstract in their future performance. When dealing in this way with the teaching of trigonometry, the expected result is improvements in basic education, later in higher education, which will return to basic education through this professional.

CONCLUSION

Thinking about the teacher's role in the teaching-learning process of Trigonometry leads directly to his role as a mediator between the classroom and the student's life, so that everything is able to make sense beyond the walls of the school. It is of paramount importance that the educator provides a favorable environment for learning with cooperation, dialogue and companionship. Researcher Michele Flávia da Silva (2015) states that, in addition, it is the role of the educator to make “learning something total and shared, a unique learning” (SILVA, 2015, p. 3).

Considering Law no. 9394/1996, which discusses objective school education, the wording of the official document shows that teaching, in elementary education, has as its main intention the “[...] preparation for the exercise of citizenship” (BRASIL, 1996), that is, the student needs to develop ethical, physical, intellectual and social skills to understand the world in which they live, be able to establish interpersonal relationships, achieve basic rights such as the right to health, education and work, and may even intervene in your reality as a citizen. Therefore, within this context, the student should be inserted in an environment that guarantees him the full right to quality learning and that promotes his social development.

In this treadmill are all the subjects that make up the curriculum of Elementary School, however, in this work it sticks to the teaching of Mathematics and its praxis, that is, its practice based on all theory. It is necessary to consider the student's prior knowledge and all the relationship that this knowledge may have with the content to be explained in the classroom. Santos and Lima (2012) state that the teaching of Mathematics must start from the daily experiences of the student for the (de)construction of concepts, aiming at a meaningful learning. If the teacher disregards this evidence, he will be nullifying the meanings of learning. [...] the

teacher, when contemplating the student's previous knowledge, will have a starting point for new learning possibilities.

Through this statement, it is possible to affirm that the objectives related to the teaching of Trigonometry in the 1st year of High School will be achieved as the teacher reflects on his pedagogical practice and rethinks his performance in the classroom to meet the needs of the student. This student is not considered a passive agent of the teaching-learning process, but the main subject in the process that must be achieved both by scientific content and by experiences in the social sphere.

There is no “recipe” for achieving the expected results through this practice. At this point, each teacher is free to choose their methodology and pedagogical approach, as long as they do not forget about the importance of creating connections between the contents and the student as a subject. The teacher's relationship with the student and vice-versa are key elements for a satisfactory learning through the presented methodologies.

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THANKS

The present work was carried out with support from the Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul – UFMS/MEC – Brazil and the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel – Brazil (Capes) – Financing Code 001.